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LET'S WORK TOGETHER

Guide to developing and sustaining user - involvement
in mental health care in South Eastern Europe

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in mental health care in South Eastern Europe

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

B&H		Bosnia and Herzegovina
CBT		Cognitive Behavioral Therapy
EU		European Union
GP		General practitioner
HCC		Health care center
CMHC		Community mental health care center
LEAP		Lived Experience Advisory Panel
LMICs		Low- and middle-income countries
NGO		Non-governmental organization
SEE		South Eastern Europe
SWOT analysis		Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (technique used in strategic planning)
ULO		User Led Organization
WHO		World Health Organization

GLOSSARY

ART THERAPY - a distinct discipline that incorporates creative expression methods through visual art media; it has originated in the fields of art and psychotherapy.

CAREGIVER - a person who takes care of his/her friend or family member affected by mental health problems.

DEINSTITUTIONALIZATION - a reform process in the system of mental health care that includes a transition from strictly institutional or hospital-based to community care.

DISABILITY, DISABLED PERSON - a physical, mental, cognitive, or developmental condition that impairs, interferes with, or limits a person's ability to engage in certain tasks or actions or participate in typical daily activities and interactions.

NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANIZATION (NGO) - any non-profit group independent of government involvement organized on a local, national or international level.

PEER SUPPORT - support provided by people with the same or similar lived experience.

PROFESSIONAL - a person involved in the health-care system or engaged in providing services in the community, e.g. doctor, psychiatrist, therapist, nurse, psychologist, psychotherapist, art therapist, social worker, etc.

PSYCHODRAMA - an action method, often used as a psychotherapy, wherein clients use spontaneous dramatization, role-playing, and dramatic self-presentation, to investigate and gain insight into their lives.

PSYCHOSOCIAL INTERVENTION - refers to therapies or actions used to improve the individual potential of people with mental disorders in their day-to-day life activities, including social and work domains.

PSYCHOTHERAPY - refers to an interpersonal intervention delivered by a trained clinician, individualized to the client's problem or modified so it can be suitable for delivery to a couple, family, or a group of clients.

PSYCHOTIC DISORDER - refers to a mental condition characterized by difficulty to distinguish what is real from what is not. People with a psychotic disorder have unusual experiences such hearing or seeing things that are not actually present and beliefs that are not shared by others. Further symptoms may include incoherent speech, non-socially appropriate behavior, memory and sleep problems, and lack of motivation to carry out daily activities. Psychosis has many different causes. Treatment may include antipsychotic medication, counseling, and social support.

Alternative definition - Psychosis is a medical term. If someone has psychosis, s/he may process the world around them differently to other people. This can include how they experience, believe or view things.

(MENTAL HEALTH CARE) USER - in this document, the term User refers to a person who was or still is a part of the health-care system as she/he was using mental health services. Sometimes this person is also referred to as “person with mental health problems”. Users - in this context of user involvement - are often regarded as “experts by experience” - since it is considered that their unique life experience in living with mental health issues is a form of expert help for others.

RESEARCHERS - professionals engaged in carrying out research activities.

SERVICE PROVIDERS - professionals and volunteers who organize programs and deliver services in the community.

SOUTH EASTERN EUROPE - a region that includes 12 countries, namely Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Kosovo*, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Romania, Serbia, and Slovenia.

STIGMA - prejudice and discrimination of mental health care users.

DESTIGMATISATION - efforts toward eliminating stigma.

USER INVOLVEMENT - active participation of a person with lived experience of mental health problems in shaping their personal health plan, organization of mental health care, and mental health research.

USER-LED ORGANIZATION (ULO) - a common term for an organization that is run and controlled by disabled people, people who use mental health services, people with learning disabilities, older people, and their families and caregivers.

SUMMARY

User involvement in mental health has been acknowledged as a ‘good thing’; however, it often remains unclear what this means and how it can be implemented in practice. This is particularly relevant for countries in South- Eastern Europe (SEE), especially those in the Balkan region, as they do not have a long tradition in user and caregiver involvement. This booklet has been produced as part of the IMPULSE research study funded by the European Commission. The project started in April 2018 with the main objective to facilitate the development of psychosocial care and treatment of people with “psychotic disorders” in five SEE countries, namely Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo*, North Macedonia, Montenegro, and Serbia.

A series of activities have been conducted within the IMPULSE project to understand how to successfully engage and empower users and caregivers in mental health care. We started by studying the current status of mental health user-led organizations/associations in five countries in SEE (during 2018-2021). This was followed by a case study of two successful user-led organizations in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Serbia. Further insights into the field were gained from studying more than 30 existing user and community organizations in the Balkans. In September 2019, the IMPULSE team organised a training workshop in Tivat, Montenegro, to facilitate establishment of a wider network of users and user organizations. Throughout the project, all activities were discussed with members of the Lived Experience Advisory Panels (LEAPs). This booklet provides a short summary of each of these activities. Insights gained from these activities were summarized in the model for successful and sustained user involvement and presented at the end of the booklet.

We hope that the booklet will be of use to mental health services users, their families, mental health care professionals and others interested in advancing mental health care. It might serve as an inspiration to those interested in working together with all relevant stakeholders to promote user involvement in clinical and non-clinical settings. This work has been conducted in five SEE countries, but as they share socio cultural background with other countries in the region, we hope our findings can be generalised to other contexts. We also hope this document could facilitate the establishment of new user-led organizations or further development of existing organizations across the SEE and globally.

INTRODUCTION

The involvement of users of mental health care can be seen in health system policy and planning processes, service provision and monitoring, and mental health research. The goal of this new, inclusive approach toward mental health care users should not be declarative, but instead, it should indicate the intention to make their voice heard. The empowerment of users and development of user associations is a process which could lead to improvements in the areas of social support, community integration, personal empowerment, quality of life, working with health professionals, employment and education, and reduction of distress symptoms. Sharing beliefs and common experiences within their associations, between peers and with supporters by favoring the principle of providing assistance related to the well-being of oneself and others, that is warm-hearted, not professional, in which everyone defines recovery for themselves, according to their own criteria, is of utter importance for their recovery. Groups led by people with mental health problems, often called ‘user-led’ groups or organizations, are crucial in giving people more choice and ability to fulfill their needs. These groups play a significant role in supporting people during the most difficult moments of life.

In the SEE, mental health care users’ involvement in any form is in early stages of development. In recent decades the region has been struck by war, poverty and isolation, which has inevitably left a profound negative impact on people’s mental health. Despite high levels of needs, these countries spend less than 5% of their health budgets on mental health care, compared to up to 13% in high-income European countries.^{1,2} Stigma, discrimination, and violation of the human rights of people with “mental illness” are still very common.³ In the Balkan countries, attempts have been made to reform mental health care, improve the human rights of patients, and transition from asylum-based to community-based care. However, despite some encouraging policy developments, in reality, many of the promised reforms have yet to be implemented.⁴

People with mental health problems and users of mental health services are the best experts for their own condition. In some free psychiatry movements, they are called “experts by experience”. There are different examples of their involvement in practice. For example, people with mental health problems can advise professionals how best to help their patients and clients.

¹ WHO, Mental Health Atlas (2014)

² WHO, Global Health Expenditure Database (2014)

³ WHO, The Mental Health Project for South Eastern Europe (2008)

⁴ Winkler, Lancet Psychiatry (2017)

Another important contribution can be seen through so-called “peer support” to other mental health care users. In national mental health strategies in many countries, such as the UK or the Netherlands, peer support is ranked as a significant factor in providing support in recovery and integration of mental health care users in the society. The evaluation from 2002 indicated a low level of NGO and user-led organization participation in terms of user involvement in SEE countries. By 2010 in most SEE countries user organizations have been established; however, their activities varied and were limited by lack of regular funding. IMPULSE is a 3-year long research study funded by the European Commission to facilitate user involvement in five countries in the Balkan region, namely Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo*, Republic of North Macedonia, Montenegro, and Serbia. IMPULSE is focused on promoting mental health care users’ and caregivers’ voices by involving them in all phases of the study.⁵

The potential benefits of this approach can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Potential benefits of active involvement of users of mental health services and caregivers in IMPULSE

⁵ This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 779334. The funding was received through the “Global Alliance for Chronic Diseases (GACD) prevention and management of mental disorders” (SCI-HCO-07-2017) funding call. More information about the study can be found on project website: <http://impulse.qmul.ac.uk/home/> and Twitter and Facebook accounts.

As part of the IMPULSE study, a series of activities has been conducted to understand how to successfully engage and empower users and caregivers in participating countries. This includes: an exploration of recent developments and type and level of user involvement in each country; case studies of two successful community organizations such as Menssana (Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina) and Prostor (Belgrade, Serbia); a short survey of other existing user and community organizations; organization of a workshop in Tivat, Montenegro in September 2019 to bring together mental health care users, professionals and researchers to facilitate establishment of a wider network of users and user organizations; and exploration of user involvement in research activities. This booklet provides a short summary of each of these activities. Insights gained from these activities were summarized in the model for successful and sustained user involvement which is presented at the end of the booklet.

Therefore, this booklet has three objectives:

- a) To describe the current state of ULOs in the SEE
- b) To share our experience with involving users and caregivers in mental health research
- c) To raise awareness and inform the public on mental health issues and human rights of users of mental health services.

WHAT IS A USER-LED ORGANIZATION (ULO)?

User-led organization (ULO) is a common term for “organization that is run and controlled by people who use support services including disabled people, people who use mental health services, people with learning disabilities, older people, and their families and caregivers” .⁶

More precisely, ULO:

- Is led and controlled by disabled people and has a minimum membership of 75 percent of disabled people on their board;
- Actively demonstrates its commitment to disabled people by employing disabled staff and volunteers;
- Actively demonstrates its commitment to the Social Model of Disability (The model that claims that people are disabled by barriers in society, not by their impairment or difference).

The beginning of this approach can be found in the 1960s, but the first formal ULO developed in the early 1980s. Since the 2000s, they have been recognized in public and popularized even by the legal health care systems, as one of the key mechanisms for design, delivery, and monitoring of resources and services to support independent living.

Some of the unique features of user-led organizations are:

- Ability to work on the field, in the local community, with local people;
- Specialists’ expertise that can help commissioners save money over the long term because of their emphasis on prevention and early treatment of mental health issues ;⁷
- They can be a unique single point of contact and information for commissioners, service providers and local service users;
- They have the ability to work with ‘hard-to-reach’ groups in involvement and consultation activities – gained trust and lived experience are helping in this task.

User-led organizations in mental health are specific because they tend to gather users of mental health services in ULO, and are also part of the concept known as community-based mental health protection.

The WHO recommends that countries restrict further investment in mental health hospitals, and make sure that adequate community-based services and services in general hospitals are in place and available for people with mental health problems.⁸ Significant parts of those alternative solutions are ULOs.

Each ULO in mental health will choose its’ own path and orientation, depending on founder choices and preferences, available resources, and general context, so they can vary from anti-psychiatry movement to being an extended part of the formal health-care system.

⁶ Social Care Institute for Excellence, UK, 2009.

⁷ Department of Health & Social Care UK, <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/department-of-health-and-social-care>, 2007.

⁸ WHO, <https://www.who.int/whr/2001/chapter4/en/index1.html>, 2001.

THE STATUS OF MENTAL HEALTH USER-LED ORGANIZATIONS / ASSOCIATIONS IN FIVE COUNTRIES IN THE SEE

As already mentioned, most SEE countries had established mental health user organizations/associations by 2010; however, their activities varied and were limited by a lack of regular funding. According to our assessment of five countries (Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo*, North Macedonia, Montenegro, and Serbia) during 2019-2020, they are at very different stages of development and functioning of mental health user-led organizations. Table 1 briefly summarizes the current situation and lists established mental health user-led organizations in each country.

Table 1 – Mental health user-led organizations (ULO) in five SEE countries during 2019/2020

COUNTRY	RECENT DEVELOPMENTS	ACTIVE MENTAL HEALTH USER-LED ORGANIZATIONS/ ASSOCIATIONS	WEB PAGES
B&H	Following the mental health system reform that has taken place in B&H since 2002, the NGO sector also responded by providing support programs for mental health care users independently in the community or in partnership with the institutions. According to our knowledge, there are seven active associations, organizing activities ranging from self-care and group psychotherapy to social entrepreneurship and life skills.	“Menssana”, Sarajevo	http://menssana-sarajevo.org/
		“Tavan”, Sarajevo	https://www.facebook.com/udruzenjetavan/
		“Fenix”, Tuzla	https://tkfenix.ba/
		“Apel Sanski Most”	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100008526641901
		“In Spe”	https://www.facebook.com/UdrugaInSpeMostar/
		“Zajedno”, Banja Luka	http://www.udruzenjezajedno.rs.sr/index.html
		“UG Zvornik”, Zvornik	https://www.facebook.com/UG-Zvornik-Zvornik-1625582567679191/

COUNTRY	RECENT DEVELOPMENTS	ACTIVE MENTAL HEALTH USER-LED ORGANIZATIONS/ ASSOCIATIONS	WEB PAGES
KOSOVO*	In the past few years, there have been many projects in Kosovo* that support the reform of the mental health system and finance work of different health organizations. According to our knowledge, there are two associations that provide services for autistic children/ people, one general patients` rights association and Dashira, active in the field of mental health. Dashira provides different support services to mental health care users and is especially successful in helping them find work.	“Autizmi flet”	https://www.facebook.com/autizmi.flet.9
		“National Autism Association of Kosovo*”	https://solidar-suisse-kos.org/gallery_post/national-association-of-autism-of-kosovo/
		“Dashira”	https://www.facebook.com/KlubiDeshiraClubhouse/
		“Patients Rights Association in Kosovo*, PRAK	https://www.facebook.com/prakkosova/posts/917602901749013/
NORTH MACEDONIA	In recent times Community mental health has become the standard for treatment of people with mental health problems in Macedonia. Some crucial steps toward community treatment have been taken, and improvements are significant in the past 2 years. This includes new community practices and the empowerment of user organizations. There is only one active ULO in this country; it has strong connections with the institutions and the university, and it is currently in the phase of growth through the IMPULSE project.	“Misla”	https://www.facebook.com/asocijacijamisla/

COUNTRY	RECENT DEVELOPMENTS	ACTIVE MENTAL HEALTH USER-LED ORGANIZATIONS/ ASSOCIATIONS	WEB PAGES
<p style="text-align: center;">MONTENEGRO</p>	<p>Up until 2019, the country did not have an established mental health user-led organization. Through activities in the IMPULSE project, a group of professionals and mental health care users came together to create a ULO. The new organization is in the formal registration process and has all the necessary resources for a successful start. Apart from that, there is one NGO in Montenegro that provides support for suicide prevention.</p>	<p>“Centar za prevenciju suicida”</p>	<p>https://www.facebook.com/centarza.prevencijusuicida/</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">SERBIA</p>	<p>A number of ULOs have been active in Serbia during the past decade. There is a formal national network of user associations called “NaUm” and most of the active ULOs are members of this network. The network itself was formed as a project result, and it does not provide any services, while most of its members gather mental health care users in different cities in Serbia. Some of these organizations are formed within mental health institutions, while others</p>	<p>“Prostor”, Belgrade</p>	<p>http://prostor.org.rs/, https://www.facebook.com/ProstorUdruzenje/</p>
		<p>Network “NaUm”</p>	<p>https://mreza-naum.org/</p>
		<p>“Dusa”, Belgrade</p>	<p>https://mreza-naum.org/udruzenje-dusa-beograd/</p>
		<p>“Videa”, Belgrade</p>	<p>https://www.facebook.com/Udru%C5%BEenje-Videa-136105573208864/</p>

COUNTRY	RECENT DEVELOPMENTS	ACTIVE MENTAL HEALTH USER-LED ORGANIZATIONS/ ASSOCIATIONS	WEB PAGES
SERBIA	operate independently in the community. The organizations located in Belgrade are the most active in providing regular services and raising public awareness.	“HC Duga”, Zrenjanin	https://www.facebook.com/humanitarni.centar.duga
		“Herc”, Belgrade	http://www.herc.org.rs/
		“Dusevna oaza”, Vrsac	https://www.facebook.com/dusevnaoaza/
		“Zrak nade”, Kovin	https://www.facebook.com/udruzenje.zraknade/

EXAMPLES OF GOOD PRACTICE IN THE SEE

User-led organizations tend to be small, under-funded and struggling to stay afloat. This is true for most countries worldwide as well as for the SEE countries. Yet, some ULOs seem to be more successful than others. In order to explore examples of successful user-led organizations in this region, we conducted two case studies during April 2019 – January 2020 with focus on mapping of the main activities of Menssana (Sarajevo, B&H) and Prostor (Belgrade, Serbia), understanding how they overcome main challenges in their work, what makes them ULOs, and what are their future aspirations. We took in consideration the continuity of providing services, level of user satisfaction, and certain sustainability as the criteria for defining success of these two organizations.

ASSOCIATION FOR MENTAL HEALTH PROTECTION MENSSANA, BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

Description:

Association for mental health Menssana is an NGO, founded in 2012, in Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina. The establishment and operation of Menssana is supported by the Mental Health Project in Bosnia and Herzegovina, and funded by the Swiss Development Agency. Initially, the association was connected to a health care center of Ilidza Municipality (part of Sarajevo). Thanks to the Memorandum of Cooperation with the Public Health Center of the Sarajevo Canton and the organization “Generation” signed in 2017, today, Menssana is conducting activities in four Mental Health Centers and the Center for Health Support "Generacija" ("Generation").

The association’s general objective is to preserve and improve mental health in the community, as well as improve the quality of life of users of mental health services. Specific objectives are:

- Undertaking actions in primary, secondary and tertiary prevention, in order to improve mental health in the community
- Organizing educational and other content to rehabilitate the users of mental health services
- Providing support to families with members with mental health problems
- Fighting the stigmatization of individuals and groups on any basis
- Encouraging the application of theoretical and applied procedures in medicine, psychology, social work, and other scientific disciplines to improve mental health in the community
- Advocating the interests of mental health professionals and mental health service users
- Encouraging the development of own publishing activities in accordance with the law
- Developing cooperation with enterprises, professional organizations, and other interested institutions and legal entities
- Care for respecting the principle of professional ethics

Funding:

Functioning and activities of the association are connected to external funding and projects, and also memberships and donations. Activities are partly funded also by selling users' handcraft.

Main activities:

Menssana is directly involved in improving quality of life for users in the local community, for years, with food and hygiene packages, organizing field trips and cultural events, and celebrating important religious and holiday dates.

The association has successfully implemented the following research projects and direct user-led projects on the field:

- One of the first projects was the anti-stigma project "Stigma Stop". The project's goal was to sensitize health workers in family medicine to mental health problems and reduce stigmatization among health workers.
- Another important project was the research project "Mental health pathway in Bosnia and Herzegovina". The project was financed by the Project for Mental Health in B&H, under the supervision of Professors Norman Sartorius and Umberto Volpe.
- The project "Green Ribbon" was also implemented to improve people's quality of life with schizophrenia and severe depression, with an emphasis on increasing social inclusion. Within the framework of this project, the organization celebrates the World Mental Health Day on October 10th.
- In 2018, Menssana became a part of the IMPULSE project.
- In 2019, Menssana successfully established the Drop-in center for mental health service users.
- In 2020, Menssana successfully produced a short played movie on the adolescent crisis.

Organization structure:

Menssana has 2 employees (both mental health professionals), 20 people on honorary engagements, 60 active members.

Overcoming main challenges:

Unlike most ULOs in the Balkans, Menssana maintained a long tradition. The main challenges were establishing links with the formal health care system and also developing independence and self-sustainment. Funding and continuation of activities are problematic for Menssana, like for many other organizations, but Menssana manages to overcome it by ongoing activities and applying for new projects, even while existing ones are running.

Why is Menssana an ULO:

The association is considered a user-led organization because it is founded and led in strong cooperation with mental health care users and

professionals. Users are part of the organizations' board, and are included and consulted in all strategic and practical decisions, as well as in project activities. In only one year (May 2019 – April 2020), more than 30 users were paid for their work in the organization.

Future development:

Menssana has been successfully connecting mental health care users, mental health professionals, local community, health care state system, and international partners. Next steps include further development of the Drop-in center, and providing services to children of users and adolescents.

This video illustrates Menssana's mission and activities:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=F1c_VSRfjR8&feature=emb_logo

NGO PROSTOR, BELGRADE, SERBIA

Description:

NGO Prostor has been working towards the development of community based services for persons with mental health problems and destigmatization of this population in Serbia since 2010. The purpose of the organization is to develop municipally recognized and supported services that cover most of the needs of persons with mental health problems: psychological, economic and social.

The general objective of the Organization is to support recovery of mental health care users through psycho-social support activities and to raise awareness and improve quality of life and social status of this group through education and campaigning.

Funding:

Prostor is funded through projects and paid services. Apart from donations, our members provide educational services for children as another financial source for the Organization. At the moment, we are carrying out two EU Erasmus + projects called "The West Balkan Hearing Voices Network" and "Community mental health practices in ex- Yugoslavia", respectively. Prostor is also a partner on the IMPULSE project, financed by the European Commission.

In the past, Prostor was supported by the Trag foundation, CNF/CEE- Cooperative of the Netherlands Foundations for Central and Eastern Europe, Serbian Ministry of culture, Norwegian and Australian Embassy in Serbia, Heartefact foundation and Erste Bank, and EU commission. In 2017/18. Prostor successfully carried out an Erasmus + KA1 project called "Hearing Voices".

Main activities:

● Activities in the community:

Over the past eight years, Prostor has provided services for persons with mental health problems through different programs in the community aiming at empowering them, supporting their re-socialization and providing psychological support. During its work, Prostor has been recognized by the institutions as a partner in mental health system reform, particularly in the deinstitutionalization process. Consequently, Prostor has officially partnered with the Belgrade municipality of Zvezdara in pioneering the development of the local Community Mental Health model in Serbia, which is now widely recognized and practiced in EU countries.

● Education:

Apart from direct work with mental health care users, Prostor has been working on the development of alternative approaches in the treatment of mental health problems through organization of educational activities for mental health professionals, persons with mental health problems, students, civil society organizations working in the field

health problems, students, civil society organizations working in the field of community mental health, and volunteers.

● Networking and collaboration:

Prostor is an official representative of the International Hearing Voices Network and one of the founders of the regional West Balkan Hearing Voices Network. “Intervoice” - the International Hearing Voices Network’s governing body is responsible for the development of the Network in Serbia and the region. The representatives of this International organization brought this alternative approach in psychiatry and the treatment of mental health conditions in the region through training for different target groups mentioned above, both in the community and in mental health institutions. These trainings were organized by Prostor on the local level and delivered by international lecturers and trainers from “Intervoice” and “Mind in Camden”, one of the English Hearing Voices representatives.

● Raising awareness:

Prostor is also active in disseminating the ideas of human rights of people with mental health problems, raising public awareness, and campaigning for the change of social status and life quality of people with the history of mental health diagnoses, as well as the change of public attitude on this subject. In the last seven years, Prostor made an impact on public attitudes through various campaigns for raising awareness on mental health issues: "Are you crazy?" campaign; regular media appearances; radio show led by Prostor staff and users that aired regularly on one national radio station; social networks, public events, collaboration with organizations, institutions, local government, individuals, on the local, national and international level.

Organization structure:

Prostor has no official employees; it is led by members, volunteers and experts hired on project bases.

Overcoming main challenges:

Main challenges include sustainability, premises, stable financing and better collaboration with institutions. Prostor uses municipality premises, far from the city center and only in certain available hours, and for office purposes they use the apartment of one of the members. This is why one of the main challenges would be to find adequate space to fulfil all needs of the organization, both staff and users. Sustainability is rather hard to achieve in the NGO sector in Serbia, and overcoming this challenge would mean good collaboration with the government (Ministries of Health and Welfare). Prostor established good collaboration with almost all mental health institutions in the past, but there is still a gap regarding patient referral to the activities in the community and more support in advocating toward government institutions.

Why is Prostor a ULO:

Professionals and volunteers lead Prostor, but mental health care users play the most crucial role in decision making regarding the choice of activities and other service quality issues. Apart from that, they lead the self-care activities and are engaged as experts by experience. The guiding principle of this organization is equality between users and service providers.

Future development:

For now, Prostor will continue to deliver regular services in the community as well as educational activities. It will also continue to develop the regional Hearing Voices Network (West Balkan HV Network) and to collaborate with other regional and international partners. One of the plans for the near future include activities for families of users in collaboration with one of Belgrade institutions, and hopefully at some point, Prostor will manage to open the first Community Center in Serbia led by NGOs and experts by experience in collaboration with institutions.

This video illustrates the work of Prostor and the situation in Serbian Community mental health through user perspective:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3Izhm5q1IKQ&t=2s>

LESSONS LEARNED FROM OTHER USER AND COMMUNITY ORGANIZATIONS

As a part of the IMPULSE study, we also conducted a short survey of other existing user and community organizations in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Serbia, Montenegro, Kosovo* and North Macedonia. We aimed to gather more information on the existing ULOs; to explore ways in which peer support can function among mental health care users, and to better understand the challenges these organizations face and their development perspectives. This work was carried out from December 2018 – March 2019.

In total 33 organizations participated in the survey, 21 in mental health and 12 in other health issues (e.g. multiple sclerosis, diabetes, impaired hearing). Most organisations were from Serbia (total number was 15) and B&H (total number was 9), while other three countries were represented by 3 organisations each.

Characteristics of the participating ULOs include:

- Most of them are oriented towards the local community; they are locally registered and cover relatively small geographical areas (such as municipality or a city). Only a few of them are active on a national level.
- These organizations may not be able to stay active for longer periods. The oldest organization was registered in 2000, and the majority were registered between 2010-2012.
- Approximately 50% percent of organizations do not have any employees, others have 1 or 2. Some of the organizations emphasized the importance of having at least one person as an employee.
- Most of the organizations rely strongly on volunteers. The numbers of volunteers vary from 2 to 70, and ULOs have an average of 5 to 10 volunteers. Some of the volunteers are relatively permanent, while the majority is included in casual activities that require a larger number of people involved (i.e., public walks, events).
- The numbers of active members/users vary from 0 to 160, on average 20 to 30.
- Most of the organizations are oriented toward direct work in the field. Only four of them deal with advocacy, system and political changes in order to improve the position of users in society.
- Non mental health ULOs defer mostly in greater family engagement and lower levels of stigmatization that opens more possibilities for organizational development.

Mission and aims of all included mental health user-led organizations falls within three main areas:

1. Direct services for users (improving life quality; improving mental health; rehabilitation; direct services and help; social networking of users)
2. Promotion of mental health in general (promoting mental health topics in public; improving legal status of mental health care users, protection of Users outside of the institution)
3. Community involvement (inclusion, resocialization, raising awareness, de-stigmatization, building capacities and educating community)

When it comes to roles and involvements of users and professionals, there are significant differences found among organizations. It is clear that strong cooperation between professionals and users is critical in achieving organizational goals since they all play different roles, as indicated in Table 2. The main challenges are listed in Table 3.

Table 2 – Defining roles of professionals and users in ULOs

PROFESSIONALS	USERS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project and organization management, ● Administration, fundraising, ● Advocacy, ensuring structure and sustainability, ● Motivating users and members, initiative for new activities and progress, ● Professional and therapeutic support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sharing of personal experience, peer support, self-help, mentoring others, ● Recruiting new members, encouragement, raising public awareness through sharing personal experience, participating in the activities, ● Logistic support in event organization, maintaining the working space and taking care of the premises.

Table 3 – Main challenges facing ULOs from different perspectives

PROFESSIONALS	USERS	ORGANIZATIONAL PERSPECTIVE	COMMUNITY PERSPECTIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● in some cases, they feel burn-out ● lack of professional support and supervision; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● occasional relapse and health issues, ● interpersonal relationships, ● lack of motivation, capacities and active participation; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● financing and sustainability, lack of specific project calls focused on financing mental health services, ● lack of institutional and government support, ● inadequate premises for the activities; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● lack of understanding and financial support from community members, ● bad reputation of NGO sector in general, ● stigma – society does not understand or is blocking activities of organizations; ● users or their families hesitate to become part of an organization because of stigma, ● corruption and misuse of finances and users, ● lack of networking with similar organizations;

When asked for recommendations and important resources for the successful functioning of user-led organizations, representatives of organizations agreed on following:

- Education and development of users, professionals and volunteers play the key role and is considered as the best investment for the organization;
- All three groups should be under continuous and adequate supervision, in order to prevent burn-out, health issues, and misuse of organization resources;
- Roles of all the three groups should be well defined, in accordance with realistic capacities, and respected in any activity;
- Organization should have as minimal resources – support from the local community, financing and space for activities;
- An organization should be well connected with the health care and social care system, local community, other relevant organizations and international partners, and networking is essential for success.
- The organization's goals should be well established, visible, and equally important and motivating for all relevant people included, and should be taken into consideration in planning activities.

BUILDING A WIDER NETWORK - WORKSHOP IN TIVAT, MONTENEGRO IN SEPTEMBER 2019

One of the important IMPULSE project activities that involve user engagement was the workshop held in Tivat, Montenegro, in September 2019. The main goal was to exchange experience between service users, professionals (volunteers/community supporters) and researchers from all partner countries, to empower the existing mental health care user organizations and to support the establishment of new organizations in the region.

Representatives of all partner countries participated; the workshop lasted for 3 days. The first day was focused on the introduction of Impulse project activities regarding user involvement and the role of mental health care users in this project and in user organizations in the region. On the second day, examples of good practices in user organizations were presented, as well as the volunteers' role in these organizations. The theory behind the importance of peer support and user organizations, as well as community organizations that deliver services for mental health care users outside of the official mental health system, was presented and explained to the participants. On day three, the most important steps were taken toward the improvement of particular situation in the field in each country. Through SWOT analysis, the team examined circumstances and conditions in each partner country, drawing conclusions and concrete ideas for improvement in all aspects.

There was a lively discussion and brainstorming, which led to some concrete steps for each country to implement in the future to either empower the existing organizations and services or to establish new ones.

Psychodrama and Art therapy techniques were used throughout the workshop.

Some of the main topics that emerged from this workshop are:

- the importance of a structured plan for starting new user organizations;
- well planned financial plan for long term period;
- importance of evaluation of the needs and level of interest and satisfaction of users;
- importance of the financial aspect, fundraising, project management, as well as sustainability (financial and institutional)- relationship with the Ministries and local governments, and local community;
- HR (the need of administrator and legal advisor) in new organizations, and also the person whose duty is to explore job opportunities for users in the organization, and be a mediator between companies and service users that are looking for work;
- premises for the organizational meetings and activities are one of the most important resources to start with;
- volunteers/ coordination and training, supervision;
- motivation of users to engage in organizational issues and contribute, but also to protect them from overload, and worsening their primary symptoms;
- working engagement of mental health care users, legal frame in different countries, possibilities; social entrepreneurship.

Evaluation results showed that most of the participants were very satisfied with the workshop and very enthusiastic regarding future collaboration and activities. Participants were also interested in networking on the regional level and consider the exchange of good practices between countries with similarly developed mental health systems to be crucial in empowerment of users and their organizations.

USER INVOLVEMENT IN RESEARCH

As mentioned, the IMPULSE study actively involved mental health care users and their caregivers in all phases of the study. At the beginning of the study, each participating country established a Lived Experience Advisory Panel (LEAP). The team received training from Dr Sally Barlow and members of the Service user and carer group advising on research (SUGAR) from the United Kingdom. The LEAP consisted of 5-8 people as experts by experience. They are invited to provide advice throughout the project, particularly on research methods, study materials, and interpretation of study findings. The LEAP meets with researchers four times a year, approximately once every three months, to discuss each project phase's results and provide feedback from a user perspective. Members were paid 20 EUR (in local currency) for participation in each meeting. This section will report two examples of topics discussed with the LEAP and how their feedback influenced research. The issue of employment and work opportunities was also discussed in these conversations, and members found it to be very relevant for them.

• **Understanding the nature of routine clinical meetings for people with “psychotic disorders”**

The IMPULSE study aims to improve the quality of regular clinical meetings in participating countries. As a starting point, we wanted to improve our understanding of current practices, and the LEAPs were among our sources of information. The LEAPs were very critical of their communication with clinicians in routine meetings. Across the participating countries, people spoke about terrible conditions in hospitals, issues regarding the legal rights of mental health patients and rather short periods, psychiatrists have on their disposal to spend with each patient, mainly discussing the medications.

Communication with doctors was particularly important for the LEAP members; usually, they do not get to discuss other topics apart from medication, and many needs of patients remain marginalized. This is why they did like the idea of facilitating dialog between patients and clinicians and discussing relevant topics other than pharmacotherapy. The LEAP members hope that this study could reduce discrimination, prejudice, and wrong attitudes displayed by some clinicians towards people with psychosis. This feedback allowed us to understand which areas are of critical importance to users. We will analyze if the study led to improvements in identified areas.

“The psychosocial intervention [in IMPULSE project] is good because it allows an individual approach to patients and minimizes the chance that the clinician goes through the meeting routinely without establishing a connection with the patient.” (LEAP member from B&H)

"I like the program [in IMPULSE project]. That is the first step towards helping solve the problems of mental health care users. It deals with the core problem of psychiatry that the psychiatrist won't listen to us. I hope this will lead to a better life of patients with less discrimination." (LEAP member from Serbia)

• **Improving materials used in research**

The IMPULSE study uses different methods to collect data, including in-depth interviews with patients and clinicians. Before conducting the interviews, we spoke to members of the LEAPs about questions that would be most relevant to service users and how to best phrase them. Their feedback was incorporated in materials we finally used to collect data.

"[IMPULSE project] was a typical research project, nothing special. The mental health patients were asked for their opinion on the project. (...) They evaluated which questions were good, how to frame questions, how to deliver this work. Just the fact that mental health patients were asked about this is huge. (...) This group maybe was not the best for this purpose. Some people were active, but others were confused and the majority was passive. Maybe you could set up clearer and more direct expectations from each member, maybe people should be asked to actively contribute before being paid for their contribution". (LEAP member from Serbia)

"Well, I joined [because] I would like to see ...that the topic of mental health is much more present in the media and outside the media. I know a lot of people who have a problem of that kind, but they are reluctant to turn to experts because, I don't know, still, as you say, a 'small community disease': what would others say, what would they think, and similar". (LEAP member from Montenegro)

• **Work and volunteering possibilities, employment and financial situation of mental health care users:**

The LEAP members appreciate the existing community services in their countries and wish they were more developed and spread. They appreciated that the IMPULSE project explores users' finances, employment and work opportunities. The LEAP members are supportive of practical activities, especially those they can use to improve their financial situation, be it through selling their art work or learning English language. The issue of work opportunities has been of particular interest during some meetings. Participants discussed how they wish to be hired according to their abilities, but they are not in a position to achieve that. There were comments regarding some more developed countries where there are many opportunities for mental health patients to get employed through medical and social care. Unfortunately, in participating countries, people still do not

have so many of these opportunities. Still, some social enterprises and NGOs provide them with the possibility to earn some extra money and feel useful, contribute to their financial situation or even their family budget. This aspect is rather important in supporting recovery.

“The income of mental health patients is miniscule, leading them to often be locked up in mental health institutions for life. What I would suggest is an existence of a space for mental health patients open throughout the year where they would create what they can according to their talent and find some sort of work, be it gardening, art, knitting and be able to sell their work throughout the year. Part of the income would go to the patients and part to maintain the center, buy materials etc. Here they could socialize, work on improving themselves, build their courage, self-image and feel useful and also to learn practical skills such as cooking and personal care.” (LEAP member from Serbia)

MODEL FOR SUCCESSFUL AND SUSTAINED USER INVOLVEMENT

User involvement can significantly advance the position of people with mental health problems in society. The most effective way to ensure service involvement seems to be through active and well-resourced user-led organizations (ULO) that can respond to specific local and national challenges. The following aspects of ULOs are crucial in ensuring their successful functioning and should be considered in settings with limited experience and resources:

- Initiated by open-minded professional(s) working in the public health care system, but with strong cooperation with users from the beginning, and with continuous collaboration of these two groups, and volunteers as well;
- Respect for users' capacities, needs, abilities and desired roles;
- Well defined roles of professionals, users and volunteers, adapted to individual capacities;
- Oriented towards field work in community, users' practical and realistic needs, and raising community awareness of benefits of user involvement;
- Supported by the local community with at least modest but adequate premises and basic financing from the beginning; important to ensure continuity of the organization between the projects;
- Able to employ at least one person;
- Provision of continuous education, development and supervision – of users, their families, professionals and volunteers, each according to their position and needs;
- Strong, continuous, and productive cooperation with the health care system;
- Engagement of a significant number of dedicated and educated volunteers;
- Building specific expertise which may include peer support, promotional activities, advocacy, advising research projects, and system and political changes in order to improve the position of users of mental health services in society;

USEFUL LINKS AND CONTACTS

- **IMPULSE PROJECT:**

<http://impulse.qmul.ac.uk/home/> and Impulse project Twitter and Facebook accounts

- **QUEEN MARY UNIVERSITY OF LONDON, United Kingdom:**

<https://www.qmul.ac.uk/>

- **MENSSANA:**

<http://www.menssana-sarajevo.org/>

- **PROSTOR:**

<http://prostor.org.rs/>

- **CLINICAL CENTER OF UNIVERSITY OF SARAJEVO, B&H:**

<https://www.kcus.ba/>

- **UNIVERSITY CLINIC OF PSYCHIATRY–SKOPJE, NORTH MACEDONIA:**

<http://medf.ukim.edu.mk/>

- **UNIVERSITY OF PRISHTINA, KOSOVO*:**

<https://www.uni-pr.edu/>

- **PSYCHIATRIC CLINIC IN PODGORICA, PODGORICA, MONTENEGRO:**

<http://impulse.qmul.ac.uk/research-and-clinical-partners/montenegro/>

- **FACULTY OF MEDICINE, UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE, BELGRADE, SERBIA:**

<http://www.mfub.bg.ac.rs/>

- **CITY UNIVERSITY LONDON, UNITED KINGDOM:**

<https://www.city.ac.uk/>

USEFUL INFORMATION ABOUT USER-LED ORGANIZATIONS AND ABOUT PLANNING USER LED APPROACH IN OTHER ORGANIZATIONS CAN BE FOUND ON FOLLOWING LINKS:

<http://www.compassdisability.org.uk/uploads/documents/ULO%20TOOLKIT.pdf>

<http://www.disabilitynottinghamshire.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2014/01/A-guide-to-user-led-organisations-ULOs.pdf>

SERVICE USER AND CARER GROUP ADVISING ON RESEARCH, CITY UNIVERSITY UNITED KINGDOM:

<https://blogs.city.ac.uk/sugar/>

WEST BALKAN HEARING VOICES NETWORK:

<http://nasglas.org/>

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